

PERIODATES OF TRIVALENT METALS.

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Reaction of trisodium paraperiodate on trivalent metallic salts has been studied and also the tetravalent lead periodate and manganese mesoperiodate.

Only few trivalent periodates are known. Eakle (*Z. Kryst.*, 1896, 16, 576) has cursorily mentioned a metaperiodate, $Al_2(IO_4)_3 \cdot 3H_2O$; Rammelsberg (*Pogg. Ann.*, 1838, 44, 559) prepared ferric mesoperiodate, $FeIO_3 \cdot 11H_2O$; Kimmins (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 55, 148) obtained tertiary ferric dimesoperiodate, FeH_3IO_9 and metaperiodate, $Fe(IO_4)_3$. Rammelsberg (*Ber.*, 1870, 3, 360) has also described a thallic periodate $3Tl_2O_3, I_2O_7, 30H_2O$.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the reaction of trisodium paraperiodate on some trivalent metallic salts and the properties of the compounds formed. Incidentally a tetravalent lead periodate and a manganese mesoperiodate were studied.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Bismuth Periodate.—Bismuth subnitrate was dissolved in concentrated nitric acid and trisodium paraperiodate, $Na_3H_2IO_6$, dissolved in dilute nitric acid, was added to it when a white precipitate was produced. It was allowed to settle and filtered, washed first with dilute nitric acid and finally with water till free from nitric acid. It was dried in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid and solid caustic potash.

Bismuth periodate formed opaque crystals, insoluble in water and mineral acids. When strongly heated, it decomposes with evolution of iodine and formation of bismuth oxide.

Bismuth was estimated as Bi_2O_3 , and iodine volumetrically. (Found : Bi, 55.48; I, 24.3. $Bi_2O_3, 2I_2O_7, 7H_2O$ requires Bi, 75.6; I, 22.5 per cent).

Aluminium Periodate.—Aluminium sulphate, dissolved in water was treated with a solution of trisodium paraperiodate in dilute nitric acid. No precipitate was formed even on concentrating the solution. So an aqueous solution of aluminium sulphate was added to a suspension of $Na_3H_2IO_6$ in water when a slight turbidity resulted. The mixture was placed over a water-bath, when after a short while, copious white precipitate was produced. It was filtered, washed with water till free from sulphate and dried in vacuum.

Aluminium periodate forms white crystals, soluble in nitric acid. On heating iodine was evolved and aluminium oxide was formed. (Found: Al, 11'06; I, 52'4. Al_2O_3 , $\text{I}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{Al}_2\text{H}_2\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11}$ {Aluminium di-para-periodate} requires Al, 11'11; I, 52'26 per cent).

Ferric Periodate.—To a nitric acid solution of trisodium paraperiodate a concentrated solution of ferric chloride was added. An immediate brown precipitate was produced. It was filtered, washed with water till free from acids, and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

The crystals are yellow and transparent, insoluble in cold and boiling water. They decompose on strongly heating. (Found: Fe, 15'9; I, 35'86. FeH_2IO_6 , $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Fe, 15'86; I, 36 per cent).

Thallic Periodate.—Thallic oxide, Tl_2O_3 , was digested with concentrated sulphuric acid and the solution was added to a nitric acid solution of $\text{Na}_3\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6$. After some time a yellowish brown precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed with dilute nitric acid and then with water till free of sulphate and dried in vacuum.

The yellowish brown crystals are insoluble in acids and decompose when strongly heated. Thallium was estimated as Tl_2O_3 . (Found: Tl, 60'5; I, 18'91. $2\text{Tl}_2\text{O}_3$, I_2O_7 , $3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Tl, 61'26; I, 19'07 per cent).

Lead Periodate.—Lead tetra-acetate, was prepared according to the modified method of Oespar and Deasy (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 792). Freshly prepared pure and dry lead tetra-acetate was dissolved in the minimum quantity of pure glacial acetic acid. The solution was cooled in ice and diluted with twice its volume of ice-cooled 40% acetic acid and to it a solution of $\text{Na}_3\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6$, dissolved in 50% acetic acid, was added drop by drop with continuous stirring. At first there was no precipitate, but after a short while a brown precipitate was formed. It was washed with 50% acetic acid by decantation and filtered through a glass gooch, where it was again washed with glacial acetic acid, and dried in vacuum.

It forms brownish opaque powder. It is acted upon by boiling water and decomposes on strongly heating. Lead was estimated as sulphate after decomposition of the salt by strong sulphuric acid, and iodine volumetrically. (Found: Pb, 44'9; I, 26'75. 2PbO_2 , I_2O_7 , $5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pb, 44'32; I, 27'19 per cent).

Manganese Mesoperiodate.—Normal manganese periodate is unknown. Rammelsberg (*Pogg. Ann.*, 1868, 134, 528) failed to prepare manganese periodate. He found that when alkali periodate was added to a solution of a Mn salt or periodic acid to MnCO_3 , a mixture of hydrated manganese dioxide and manganese iodate was obtained

A thin paste of an excess of Ag_2IO_3 was taken in a beaker, placed in a freezing mixture. An ice-cold solution of MnCl_2 was quickly poured into the beaker. Reaction took place with formation of silver chloride and a pink solution. The liquid was quickly filtered by a filter pump through a funnel surrounded by ice and the filtrate was collected in a beaker, which was placed in ice. The beaker was kept in a vacuum desiccator, containing concentrated sulphuric acid and solid caustic potash and kept in a refrigerator, the temperature of which was never above 15° . After two days beautiful pink crystals were formed. They were quickly filtered and dried in the vacuum desiccator kept in the refrigerator.

The crystals were stable below 15° , but above that temperature decomposed into black manganese hydroxide. Iodine was estimated volumetrically and manganese as Mn_2O_3 . [Found Mn, 28.70; I, 42.66. $\text{Mn}_2(\text{IO}_3)_2$ or $3\text{MnO}\cdot\text{I}_2\text{O}_7$, requires Mn, 28.5; I, 43.9 per cent].

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